

Search String:

("Requirement Analysis" OR "Requirement Specification" OR "Requirement Validation" OR "Requirement Elicitation" OR "Requirement Management" OR "Functional Requirement" OR "Functional Requirements" OR "Non-Functional Requirement" OR "Non-Functional Requirements") AND (ambigu* OR vague*) AND (resolv* OR detect* OR measur* OR evaluat* OR automat* OR "artificial intelligence" OR AI OR "machine learning" OR "natural language processing" OR NLP OR tool OR technique OR method OR framework OR model OR strateg*)